

NFDI4Earth Report

Workshop Report: NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture

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Executive Summary

The Task Area 3 2interoperate of the NFDI4Earth is responsible for developing the NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture, and was holding a one-day workshop in April 2025. In the first part of the NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture workshop, the NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture was adopted as a three-pillar concept, consisting of the pillars 'Community Services', 'NFDI4Earth Service', and 'Basic IT Services' with assigned building blocks. Several objectives were defined for future work. Firstly, the concept and description of the building blocks are to be published as articles in a collection of the NFDI4Earth Living Handbook (LHB) so that it can form the basis for a NFDI4Earth-related terminology. Secondly, each of these building block will be curated by assigned experts, with the additional task of expanding the collection of relevant implementation and standard examples wherever possible. Thirdly, the interconnection between building blocks needs to be developed. The result of these processes should be an ontology. In this process we will include the role of the NFDI4Earth label, the achievements of Base4NFDI¹ and EOSC². The NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture should be seen as a living and continuously adapted architecture in an editorial process.

In the second part of the workshop, to further the architecture synthesis process, Data as a Service³ (DaaS) was identified as a primary interoperability enabling principle of data infrastructures. It was discussed, how this principle can be established and promoted within NFDI4Earth and the ESS community. The workshop outcome suggests to formulate a clear vision and initiate a community process with providers, integrating user needs for a targeted development of NFDI4Earth community services in that direction. Information on benefits and examples for DaaS that ideally support all FAIR guiding principles should be promoted in NFDI4Earth. Central for the adoption of services would be a DaaS recommendations document. To identify candidate service providers that are capable to adapt to DaaS, a set of criteria were proposed, ranging from data curation, interface standards, stable long-term operation to code snippets for integration of DaaS in scientific workflows. The benefits of providing Workflow Management Systems (WMS) were highlighted as another catalyst for potential interoperability improvements. A key issue in this respect is the need for very detailed metadata, i.e., allowing to plug data into standardised processing steps that a WMS controls. Furthermore, the software tools to be integrated in WMS require special consideration on public availability. On top of these aspects, facing the broad range of different application fields and possible use cases, introducing WMS as a NFDI4Earth service constitutes intrinsically a complex and resource intensive undertaking.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/15464073>

² <https://eosc.eu/>

³ In contrast to data as files to download: The Earth Data Portal (<https://earth-data.de/>) is an example for this, where data from distributed OGC-data services are bundled in an interoperative way as thematic viewers.

The third part of the NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture workshop focused on defining and improving information flows and integration mechanisms across the architecture's services. A central aspect was the onboarding process for stakeholders and services, aiming to clarify how new contributors can be integrated into the NFDI4Earth ecosystem effectively and sustainably.

Key outcomes include the need for a structured, target group-specific onboarding approach, guided by stakeholder personas and real-world use cases. The participants of the workshop emphasised the importance of personal, proactive engagement strategies tailored to the unique needs of each stakeholder group and defined e.g., promotional materials as critical tools to support onboarding. Conceptually, onboarding was not seen as a simple invitation, but rather as a curated, expert-guided process requiring a preparatory review phase and flexible support mechanisms.

Proposals to operationalise onboarding within the Synthesis Architecture included mapping onboarding steps to existing service building blocks, prioritising key service types (e.g. metadata catalogues and repositories), engaging internal experts responsible for each building block and defining dependencies and integration paths. Before formal onboarding, a pre-onboarding questionnaire should be deployed to capture stakeholder needs. An ontology-driven approach was proposed to support this mapping.

Overall, this session emphasised the importance of alignment between technical architecture and user-facing processes. Onboarding acts as both a gateway and a quality filter, ensuring that services and stakeholders align with NFDI4Earth's interoperability goals and long-term FAIR data vision.

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Introduction

The NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture deals with the design of an overarching NFDI4Earth Architecture. The NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture is structured in the three-pillars: (i) Community Services, (ii) NFDI4Earth Services, and (iii) Basic IT Services. These pillars consist of building blocks such as a Data Portal, Registry for Infrastructures and Services, or Middleware Services. These are depicted in **Fig 1**.

Figure 1: NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture sketched as three pillars and building blocks.

Overview

The Task Area 3 2interoperate of the NFDI4Earth is responsible for developing the NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture. We recently described in the Deliverable 'D3.1.3 Improved version of the architecture based on new pilots and other community services'⁴ our updated version of the NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture, which is based on new results from pilots and other community services. This report presents the results from a one-day in-person workshop on 1 April 2025 in Bremen to discuss recent findings regarding the NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture and how to develop it further.

Workshop Program

The one-day workshop agenda was designed to propagate recent ideas and develop a future strategy to involve the community better.

⁴ https://sharepoint.tu-dresden.de/projects/nfdi4earth/_layouts/15/WopiFrame.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B7C93BCD8-2D11-4E0E-8CDA-977B57A2E826%7D&file=D3_1_3%20Improved%20version%20of%20the%20architecture%20Subm.pdf&action=default&List=1&ListId=%7B87621D08-D04B-4067-BF4E-2DB0A05CCC3F%7D&ListItemId=3534

The in-person workshop was attended by 10 participants, 3 external participants took part remotely via Zoom. The participants were either members of the Task Area 3, or involved in related projects such as the BITS terminology or the Helmholtz Data Hub.

Introduction and Impulses

The workshop topics were split in three parts:

Part 1: NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture Status Quo and Tools for ontology development

In several previous meetings we developed a NFDI4Earth building block concept. These building blocks were already described in a rather generic way in the Deliverable D3.1.3. On site, the workshop participants were introduced to these ideas in a short impulse talk. The impulse talk was followed by a discussion of the following questions:

- NFDI4Earth Service Architecture building blocks: How can we describe the building blocks in digital form (terminology service)?
- Can this be developed in some form of ontology?
- Can we find editors for single building blocks or a group of building blocks?

Part 2: Data as a Service - Impact of the architecture on the community embedding

In this part of the workshop, we were looking at the relations between building blocks of the architecture, such as middleware and processing tools, and their embedding in the community. The integration of Spatial Data Infrastructures with their APIs is a good example for data provision as a service for usage in ESS data workflows, rather than data provision for download from webservicees.

We want to develop a strategy, how to concretise recommendations/ key standards and services to onboard community services. How should NFDI4Earth promote Data as a Service at the RDM service providers? How can NFDI4Earth identify service providers that are capable to adapt? How to assess the potential impact of different workflow management systems on interoperability? Can we adopt e.g., Galaxy Earth System⁵ workflow management and claim an EOSC-node strategy?

The online participants used a Miroboard for their discussion, while the participants in the room discussed at three stations of a board with written cards in groups of 3-4 individuals. Each group discussed for 10 min the respective question.

⁵ <https://earth-system.usegalaxy.eu/>

The groups circulated at the three stations (one per guiding bullet) to discuss and answer each question, and develop realistic actions for the task area.

The following questions were discussed in these groups.

Question 1: How should NFDI4Earth promote Data as a Service at the RDM service providers?

Question 2: How can NFDI4Earth identify service providers that are capable to adapt?

Question 3: How to assess the potential impact of different workflow management systems on interoperability? Can we adopt e.g. Galaxy Earth System and claim a EOSC-node strategy?

Part 3: Information flows and connections among the architecture services

This requires a high-level description of how services can be integrated, what can be integrated, what are the requirements. How will this be related to the label, and on-boarding process (next steps, etc.)

To involve the workshop participants more in this specific topic, the Measure M3.3 introduced it with a presentation. The proposed onboarding process is sketched in **Fig. 2**.

Onboarding

Figure 2 Proposed Onboarding Process

The measures M3.3 or M3.4 are initiating the onboarding by making an offer to national and international stakeholders. If a stakeholder is interested in the NFDI4Earth services or wishes to contribute their own resources, M3.3 and M3.4 facilitate connections between them and the appropriate service representatives.

Collaboration between the community service blocks and basic IT services must be documented in Living Handbook articles. If stakeholders provide software or data repositories, the Knowledge Hub can harvest their metadata. Meanwhile, the NFDI4Earth Label can evaluate these repositories and, upon successful review, issue official NFDI4Earth labels. All onboarding-related information will be made available through the OneStop4All.

As part of the discussion tree, questions related to the onboarding process were prepared in advance. Three questions were assigned to three in-person groups, each of which held discussions at designated poster boards. The online group addressed the same questions as Group II. The discussions lasted 20 min.

Group I: This task involved that a number of different stakeholder stories are created, i.e., describe the situation and needs of various stakeholders, create a detailed persona, including background, goals, plan points, and expectations.

Group II: This task was integrating/mapping the onboarding into/on the synthesis architecture based on the understanding of the synthesis architecture. If there is any need to adjust the synthesis architecture to facilitate this integration/mapping. Develop an ontology.

Group III: The task is to illustrate the architecture to new stakeholders as part of the onboarding material.

The participants were asked: Imagine you are a State Data Gateway (SDG) or running state data infrastructure, what kind of promotional material would you be interested in? How would you like the architecture to be presented? Design such promotional material based on your findings.

- Promotional video for onboarding of Stakeholders (define length, structure storyline, write a plot description for each video sequence)
- Promotional flyer design (define the flyer style and language, visual and textual elements)
- LHB article structure on the onboarding workflow topic (structure an article, define the tone)

Outcome

Part 1: NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture Status Quo and Tools for ontology development

In the discussion it was highlighted that a description or definition of the NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture is needed and a first sketch was formulated along the tasks. The NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture is regarded as an

approach, which sorts the various internal NFDI4Earth services (products) and external services in sensible groups. It provides a terminology to describe all services, published as a collection in the LHB (Living Handbook). Connections and dependencies between the services will in the future be described and sketched in an ontology. Within the NFDI4Earth there will be experts assigned to each of the building blocks. Supported standards, and interfaces are added, and dependencies are defined and where necessary deposited in the NFDI4Earth label. It is a living and continuously developed architecture in an editorial process.

The tasks derived from the discussion are thus:

- The general definition of the NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture needs to be improved and extended
- Already published Deliverables, such as the Deliverable 'D3.1.3 Improved version of the architecture based on new pilots and other community services'⁶ will be used to create a Living Handbook Collection, including the description of the building blocks as articles.
- The target groups (users, service providers, ...) have to be specified further.
- An NFDI4Earth expert will be assigned to each of the building block to facilitate the onboarding process.
- The relations between the building blocks will be defined. They will show dependencies of building blocks and services in respect to interoperability.
- EOSC sources on interoperability levels will be taken into account⁷, as well as the NFDI Core Ontology, and the NFDI4Earth ontology⁸
- The building block sketch (**Fig 1.**) will be updated on a regular basis
- Reference implementations for interoperability will be collected and provided. This will help to guide service providers, and show how these can be implemented
- NFDI Basic Services and EOSC services will be strongly taken into account.

Part 2: Data as a Service - Impact of the architecture on the community embedding

In the second part regarding the first question "How should NFDI4Earth promote Data as a Service at the RDM service providers?" the following feedback was given.

⁶ https://sharepoint.tu-dresden.de/projects/nfdi4earth/_layouts/15/WopiFrame.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B7C93BCD8-2D11-4E0E-8CDA-977B57A2E826%7D&file=D3_1_3%20Improved%20version%20of%20the%20architecture%20Subm.pdf&action=default&List=1&ListId=%7B87621D08-D04B-4067-BF4E-2DB0A05CCC3F%7D&ListItemId=3534

⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d787ea54-6a87-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁸ <https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/knowledgehub/nfdi4earth-kh-schema/>

Data as a Service (DaaS) has to be effectively promoted to RDM service providers to establish it as a principle within the NFDI4Earth and the ESS community. In real-life use cases and actual user stories it is suggested to showcase, where DaaS has significantly enhanced data workflows, accessibility, or reuse. This can be emphasised with cross-institutional success stories involving FAIR-aligned data sharing and reuse. The obvious benefits should be demonstrated by highlighting specific scientific domains or research groups where DaaS is a clear necessity, e.g., environmental sciences, climate modelling, or biodiversity studies. By bundling the data, an increase of data interoperability and adherence to the complete FAIR guiding principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) should be addressed. DaaS as a foundational element of long-term, FAIR-aligned data stewardship should be positioned. Clear recommendation documents should be created to provide a concise recommendations paper targeted at RDM service providers, which outlines an integration path for DaaS. This can be outlined in the NFDI4Earth Synthesis Architecture. Further, the DaaS promotion can be interlinked with existing infrastructures and RDM tools. As examples were mentioned the RDMO for planning, the TIB, or PANGAEA as a domain-specific repository.

In summary by combining **real-life use cases, strategic communication, and FAIR-based value framing**, NFDI4Earth can drive adoption and integration of Data as a Service across the RDM ecosystem.

The Miroboard Group developed the following outcome:

Figure 3 Outcome as sketched by the Miroboard online participants

The outcome of the Miroboard participants had a different focus. As can be seen in **Fig.3**, to successfully promote Data as a Service (DaaS) at RDM service providers, NFDI4Earth should adopt a strategic, community-driven approach that emphasises coordination, vision, and usability. As already discussed before, the Miroboard group also sketched actions, which position DaaS as an integral part of RDM:

First of all, the examples of good practise provided from (other) communities should be communicated as a vision. A conceptual framework should be developed in a community process with other providers, where the core properties and architecture of DaaS can be defined. This can include access mechanisms (e.g., APIs, DOI resolution), metadata standards, licensing and reuse models, and integration into RDM planning and publishing workflows. This has to be aligned with the roadmap of the providers. RDM service providers have to be integrated to synchronise the development path. It has to be ensured that the roadmap aligns with the user needs, which then have to be communicated to the services providers. A concept has to be developed that describes the properties of Data as a Service. In the end, examples of good practices from the own community should be provided or good practices from the broader community (e.g., EOSC, NFDI in general, or international initiatives) should be shared. Here successful DaaS implementations and adoption stories from the NFDI4Earth community itself can be highlighted. The DaaS solutions can be made discoverable and accessible via the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub and OneStop4All (OS4A).

This multi-pronged strategy will ensure that DaaS is not only promoted effectively, but embedded sustainably in the evolving RDM ecosystem, guided by user needs, collaborative development, and a shared vision for open, FAIR-aligned research.

Regarding the **second question** “How can NFDI4Earth identify service providers that are capable to adapt?” the following feedback was given:

To identify service providers that are capable of adapting to the evolving needs of Earth System Science (ESS), NFDI4Earth should apply a criteria-driven approach that evaluates both technical readiness and strategic alignment with scientific and operational goals.

First of all, the purpose has to be clarified and the aim of adaptation has to be defined —whether it is for a technical function (e.g., data interoperability, software deployment) or an operational one (e.g., user support, service sustainability). According to this the evaluation criteria have to be tailored.

The focus should be on current and urgent themes, and prioritise on providers, who are responsive to urgent Earth system topics such as climate change, extreme weather events, or earthquakes. The emphasis could be on those already engaged with real-time data processing, scenario modelling, or event-based response systems.

The technical readiness and experience have to be assessed, and the technical level and maturity of the service provider evaluated. This includes, whether they are experienced in data delivery, service APIs, and long-term preservation. Further, it can be clarified whether standardised metadata schemas, open formats, and stable interfaces are support.

It should be ensured that provider diversity is embraced by including a broad range of providers—large institutions, domain-specific repositories, and community-led services—to reflect the diversity of ESS communities.

Preference should be given to providers with a strong data and metadata curation workflows that ensure data quality and consistency, long-term usability and documentation.

Added value can be achieved through simplicity and connectedness, using simple, intuitive interfaces, integrating tools for data access, visualisation, and transformation, as well as connected services across the research lifecycle.

Infrastructures can be favoured that can offer data as a service (DaaS), including editable code snippets or Jupyter notebooks.

Further, service providers can be prioritised that implement standardised interfaces and metadata protocols. Stability should be demonstrated through long-term funding models, community governance, and reliable uptime.

NFDI4Earth can identify capable and adaptable service providers by combining technical assessments, community inclusion, and strategic alignment with urgent scientific needs.

The Miroboard participants developed the following results:

These participants were of the opinion that a community approach was needed, which strongly relates to a service portfolio. They rated that the NFDI4Earth label process and activities are strongly related. They are also pointing out a gap between powerful `bigger repositories´ and small niche repositories.

In this regard, the Miroboard participants formulated questions for the NFDI4Earth to identify adaptable service providers, such as:

- Who can act as multiplier/ initially set up the envisioned service?
- How can NFDI4Earth motivate?
- How can NFDI4Earth bring providers together?
- How can NFDI4Earth support?
- How to make sure that we do not lose providers?

In the **third question** “How to assess the potential impact of different workflow management systems on interoperability? Can we adopt e.g. Galaxy Earth System⁹ and claim a EOSC-node strategy¹⁰?” the feedback was that that domain specific and best practise examples are needed to evaluate the software. Further some aspects have to be checked, such as the way the software tools are published and

⁹ <https://earth-system.usegalaxy.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about/building-the-eosc-federation/contributing-to-the-build-up-phase/>

the interfaces. In this respect very detailed metadata is needed. A Workflow Management System (WMS) should contain standardised interfaces, metadata and terminologies. As a product specific example, the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM)¹¹ as a product specific format was given. Further, the Ocean Data View Website (ODV)¹² was discussed as a good example from the Alfred Wegener Institute. Initially it was partly funded. There are interviews held about the onboarding of this service at EOSC and Galaxy Earth System (Sebastian Mieruch, AWI). It was seen as very critical to find best use case partners of workflow engines.

There was no input from the Miroboard participants on this question.

Part 3: Information flows and connections among the architecture services

Group I: Make a number of different stakeholder stories, i.e., describe the situation and needs of various stakeholders, create a detailed persona, including background, goals, pain points, and expectations.

Systematically analysing typical stakeholder perspectives helps identify the specific needs, goals and challenges of different actors in the run-up to the onboarding process. Two exemplary stakeholder personas were used to map the spectrum of relevant requirements, enabling conclusions to be drawn regarding the design of a target group-oriented onboarding process.

Research data management at state level:

State geological surveys are a typical example of a federally structured, data-holding institution. While these organisations typically have well-established data collection and annotation processes based on ISO standards, they tend to rely on simple, low-maintenance solutions. There was a clear articulation of the desire for automated data reconciliation, for example via middleware components. Personal contacts and targeted, repeated communication were identified as key to successful engagement. Taking a coordinated, active approach to engaging with individual state agencies was deemed a necessary first step to clarify work structures and deficits. In this context, reference was made to the successful approaches of other NFDI consortia, such as NFDI4Objects, whose decentralised networking strategies could be emulated.

¹¹ <https://academic.oup.com/database/article/doi/10.1093/database/baac035/6591806>

¹² <https://webodv.awi.de/>

The Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (BSH):

The BSH¹³ is an institution with many years of domain-specific data expertise and an existing network of contacts in the European context (e.g., via SeaDataNet¹⁴). Long-standing, trusting cooperation was cited as the basis for successful integration here. Participation in committees such as the DFG Senate Commission for Oceanography (now Begutachtungspanel Forschungsschiffe¹⁵ - GPF) highlights the institutional commitment. These framework conditions favour trusting cooperation. At the same time, they demonstrate that the onboarding process should build upon existing professional cooperation and take existing structures into account.

The personas and scenarios developed provide several key insights for the further development of the NFDI4Earth onboarding process:

- Target group-specific approach: The onboarding process should be tailored to specific groups of stakeholders. A standardised approach is insufficient; individual entry points, expectations, and previous experience must be considered instead.
- Integration of existing best practices: The methods of successful partner consortia should be analysed systematically and adapted as necessary, especially with regard to direct communication formats.
- Personal communication and coordination: Robust communication relationships are a key success factor. This requires a coordinated strategy for contacting and supporting stakeholders through dedicated contact persons within the consortium.
- Involvement in architecture development: The derived personas can be used to specify requirements for specific building blocks (e.g. middleware and metadata catalogues), thus establishing onboarding as a functional component of the synthesis architecture.

Group II: Based on your understanding of the synthesis architecture, integrate/map the onboarding into/on the synthesis architecture. Is there any need to adjust the synthesis architecture to facilitate this integration/mapping? Develop an ontology.

1. Purpose of Onboarding in NFDI4Earth

Onboarding in NFDI4Earth is a guided process designed to help users or providers understand, adopt, and integrate services into the infrastructure. It begins with a pre-onboarding questionnaire to capture stakeholder needs, expectations, and

¹³ https://www.bsh.de/DE/Home/home_node.html

¹⁴ <https://www.seadatanet.org/>

¹⁵ <https://www.portal-forschungsschiffe.de/fahrtvorschlaege-begutachtung.html>

technical context. This step enables the assignment of domain-specific experts from relevant architectural building blocks.

Onboarding is not triggered merely by visibility demands. It requires a minimum level of dialogue and commitment, such as offering a data service, repository, or database. The process includes account setup, tutorials, documentation, and support, and varies depending on whether the stakeholder is using or providing a service. It should be adaptive, like a route planner, to accommodate diverse stakeholder roles and service types.

2. Onboarding Workflow and Architecture Integration

The onboarding workflow includes a pre-onboarding phase that features a review process to assess alignment between stakeholder contributions and NFDI4Earth's goals. This ensures mutual benefit and strategic fit.

Measure 3.1 can help determine where onboarding best integrates into the synthesis architecture. It might be necessary to embed onboarding into the NFDI4Earth Service Platform. It was proposed that users should actively initiate onboarding by requesting a "ticket" rather than the process being initiated by the consortium.

3. Stakeholder Registry and Contribution Tracking

There is a recognised need for a registry of onboarded stakeholders and their contributions. This registry would be useful for architectural transparency, collaboration monitoring, and coordination.

The registry could differentiate between:

- Content contributors (e.g., those publishing to LHB),
- Data contributors (e.g., repositories and datasets),
- Interoperability conductors (e.g., those linking systems or services).

However, creating and maintaining such a registry is complex and would require clear definitions, ongoing updates, and governance.

4. Partner Requirements

Stakeholders expected to onboard should ideally bring:

- Domain or technical expertise
- A service that aligns with NFDI4Earth goals
- The ability to organise or contribute to interest groups

The onboarding process should prioritise integration of key service types, such as data repositories, metadata catalogues, portals, and databases. For complex or large-scale services like AI platforms or middleware, internal experts should be onboarded first to ensure successful integration and support.

5. Final Considerations

The onboarding process must be simple, clear, and well-documented to help service providers understand where they fit in the ecosystem. It should include structured visuals or diagrams to show relationships among services, dependencies, and required interfaces. The overall goal is to establish a transparent, scalable, and stakeholder-responsive integration mechanism within NFDI4Earth.

Group III:

Question: Imagine you are a State Data Gateway (SDG) or running state data infrastructure, what kind of promotional material would you be interested in? How would you like the architecture to be presented? Design such promotional material based on your findings.

1. Promotional video for onboarding of Stakeholders (define length, structure storyline, write a plot description for each video sequence)
2. Promotional flyer design (define the flyer style and language, visual and textual elements)
3. LHB article structure on the onboarding workflow topic (structure an article, define the tone)

Conclusion 1: *The group found that the promotional flyer was the most needed material. A video might be less effective due to low viewership (e.g., YouTube). Written materials like the LHB articles reach a more engaged audience. The group worked on a poster wall to develop the pathway to an effective flyer design for the next funding phase.*

Key considerations for a flyer design proposed by the participants:

- **Target Audience Analysis:** Define relevant personas and their specific needs. Similar to how it is done for software product development.
- **Language:** Use clear, accessible English throughout.
- **Flyer Purpose:** Promotional material introducing NFDI4Earth and its onboarding offer.
- **Cross-Linking:** Include a QR code that links to the Living Handbook (LHB) article and the other NFDI4Earth posters for additional information.

- **Diverse Perspectives:** Since stakeholders view NFDI4Earth from different angles, varied communication approaches are necessary.

Conclusion 2: *The group concluded that the flyer should be targeted towards the user, and enhance the visibility of NFDI4Earth. As right now a flyer exists, this flyer needs to be integrated as well in the new design to see what worked and what did not work with the current flyer. The group work did not allow to go into the details needed for writing the texts or graphics for a new flyer. The timing for the new flyer needs to be well-placed with regard to the next funding phase. The results obtained here can then be useful.*

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